

Appendix

Woldia University

Faculty of Business and Economics

Department of economics

Dear respondents, this questionnaire is prepared by the research team of Department of Economics, Woldia University to study “The determinants of onion production in Raya Kobo District, Amhara Regional State of Ethiopia”. The information you are going to provide will be used primarily for the study only. Therefore, you are kindly requested to give genuine information for all the questions you are required to answer. We would like to thank you in advance for your cooperation.

General Direction:

- Do not write your name,
- For closed ended questions, mark (✓) in a given space, and for open ended questions give short and precise answer.

1. Gender of respondents Male Female
2. Age of respondents _____ (in years)
3. Educational level, Illiterate Grade 1-8 Grade 9-12 Above Grade 12
4. Number of Family size: _____ (in number)
5. Number of active labour force of the household _____ (in number)
6. Total oxen size of the household _____ (in number)
7. Did you participate in off-farm income generating activities? Yes No
8. If you say yes for the above question, how much income did you earn _____ ETB
9. What are the sources of off-farm activities? _____
10. How much total crop land do you have? _____ in hectare.
11. What size of land did you plough to produce onion during the cropping season? _____ in ha
12. How many oxen did you have to produce onion? _____ in number
13. How long have you practiced production of onion products? ___ Years
14. How much quintals of onion did you produce? _____ in quintals
15. Have you ever used fertilizer for the production of onion? Yes No
16. Did you get fertilizer at the right time? Yes No
17. If your answer for Q.16 is No, what was the main reason behind?
Lack of access Price expensiveness
Lack of awareness other (specify) _____
18. Did you use compost/manure for production of onion? Yes No
19. If your answer for the above question is no, what is the reason for didn't using compost? _____

20. Did you have an access to credit in the stated year? Yes No
21. If your answer for Q.20 is Yes, how much did you get? _____ (in birr)

22. If your answer for Q.20 is No. what are reasons? Limited supply of credit High collateral Huge bureaucracy Others (specify) _____
23. What alternatives have you applied to solve fertilizer and other inputs shortage? Addressing the amount we get Purchasing from merchants at higher prices Purchasing before and store
- Used organic fertilizer in addition to Inorganic fertilizer
- other _____
24. Are you a member of farm cooperatives? Yes No
25. If you say yes for Q 24, what type of services did you get from it?
Obtain Inputs Advise service Obtain improved onion Seed
- others _____
26. Have you ever get extension contact on onion production practices? Yes No
27. If your answer for Q.26 is No, why? (✓) (Multiple responses is possible), No service provider nearby Lack of Awareness Do not have time to get the service Nothing knowledge added thru extension
- Others (specify) _____
28. How frequent were you got extension service last year? (✓) Once per month Twice per month Three times per month Four times per month Others, specify _____
29. Did you use herbicide in the onion production in the given year? Yes No
30. Did you apply chemical pesticide at your onion plant? Yes No
31. If your answer is no for Q 29/30 above, what is the main reason behind? a. lack of availability b. price expensiveness c. lack of awareness d. other specifies _____
32. What type of alternatives to solve the problem of fertilizer and other inputs shortage
33. What type of soil your onion land did have? Most fertile fertile least fertile
34. Did you have access to irrigation water to produce onion? Yes No
35. If you say yes for Q. 34, did you get sufficient irrigation water? Yes No
36. If you say no for Q. 34/5, how frequent were you got irrigation water?
< 7 days 7-10 days 11-14 days above 15 days
37. For how many times did you plough your onion field before transplanting your onion plant from the nursery bed? _____
38. For how many times did you hoe the onion plant field after transplantation? _____
39. For how many times did you employ chemical fertilizer after transplantation? _____
40. What are the major challenges of producing onion in your area?
Similar planting period Labour cost Rain at harvesting time Crop Disease
Inputs shortage Inappropriate use of inputs High input cost Lack of awareness on storage method Infertility of soil Shortage of land Insufficient irrigation water
- Other _____